

A Neutrosophic Statistic Method to Predict Tax Time Series in Ecuador

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Abstract. Prediction of tax collection behavior is an essential tool for social planning by the State of any country. The tax is the State's mechanism for budget collection, which is necessary to accomplish public services that benefit the whole society. This paper firstly aims to propose a method of predicting time series where values can be given in form of intervals rather than numbers. This form permits to obtain more truthful results, but with a greater indeterminacy. Because statistical prediction methods are used, where data in form of intervals are included, we can classify this approach as a kind of Neutrosophic Statistics technique. Basically, the method converts a set of predicted numerical values into intervals. The second objective is to apply the method to predict the monthly income from taxes in Ecuador for the year 2019.

Keywords: time series, tax, prediction, neutrosophic statistic, autocorrelation, median average

1 Introduction

The tax is a kind of tribute regulated by the public law, see [1]. Taxes generally have the State as a creditor and aims to finance state expenditures. These are based on the principle that those who have more are those who must contribute more, in order to guarantee equity and social freedom.

People and companies must pay taxes on a mandatory basis, because this is the way to finance the operation of the State, otherwise it would collapse. This is the mechanism to guarantee the building of infrastructure such as roads, ports, airports, hydraulic and electrical installations, to provide public health, education, defense, social security services, as support for the unemployed, disability benefits or occupational accidents, the payment of pensions, among many other essential aspects of society.

Some kind of taxes are income taxes, capital gains and profits, social security contributions by workers, employers and freelancers, payroll taxes, taxes for the property, and goods and services taxes.

In this paper, the prediction of taxes in Ecuador is made for the year 2019. For this, we start from the monthly measurement of the sum of income taxes, consumption taxes and value-added taxes. Thus, we propose and apply a neutrosophic method of time series prediction, which differs from those appeared in [2-4]. Such a method uses a set of statistical techniques to obtain classical numeric values to form intervals that have as a limit the lowest and highest values of all the individual considered methods. So, predictions are based on intervals rather than numeric values.

The problem of predicting has a certain complexity; therefore there exist many methods to predict future values, see [5-12]. This quantity of tools is due to the fact that each of them is effective for a set of cases, while for others it is not. Moreover, the most elementary methods can guarantee better results than the more sophisticated ones. That is why the integration of the results of the methods can give more acceptable results than if each one is used separately.

Thus, we offer to increase the probability of obtaining a more truthful result, in exchange for increasing indeterminacy. This corresponds to the Theory of Neutrosophic Statistics, where models and parameters are applied over intervals instead of numerical values, see [13][1].

This method is applied to solve the tax prediction problem in Ecuador. This prediction is essential, because it allows social planning by the Ecuadorian State. It will be possible to estimate in advance the income that the State will have for taxes. This approach is based on the principle that the given information in form of intervals is useful for public administration in this way.

This paper is divided as follows; it begins with a section where the classic statistical concepts and methods of time series are explained, as well as the essential ideas of the theory of Neutrosophic Statistics. The proposed prediction method is next presented and applied to the tax prediction problem in Ecuador. We finish with the

section of conclusions.

2 Preliminaries

This section summarizes the theory of statistical methods of time series and neutrosophic statistic theory divided in two subsections.

2.1 Times Series

A *time series* is a gathering of observations made consecutively in time, see [14-17][2].

When observations are made continuously in time, time series is called *continuous*. Whereas, when the observations are taken only at specific moment of times it is called *discrete*, usually time variable are equally spaced. If time series can be predicted exactly it is called *deterministic*, however future values of most of time series can only be partially predicted by past values, and they are called *stochastic*.

Among the objectives to study time series, in this paper we select the *prediction or forecasting*, which is the calculus in advance of future values of the series since the past values.

Time series can have the following components:

- Seasonal effect* is manifested when time series fluctuates in short-term periods. In annual time series they correspond to changes in periods shorter than one year.
- Cyclic changes* occur when the time series oscillates with not fixed long-term periods. In annual time series these cycles correspond to oscillations in many years.
- Trend* is a long-run development. This component can be interpreted like the overall tendency of the series when oscillations are not considered.
- A component that does not correspond to any of the previous ones, which is called *residual*.

Many fields of knowledge are used in time series forecasting, we select particularly a statistical approach.

A time series is called *strictly stationary* if the joint distribution of $X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, \dots, X_{t_n}$ is the same as the joint distribution of $X_{t_1+q}, X_{t_2+q}, \dots, X_{t_n+q}$ for every t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n, q .

In the following we consider *normal stationary processes*, and we use the estimated coefficients and statistics of this kind of process. A *normal process* is such that the joint distribution of $X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, \dots, X_{t_n}$ is a multivariate normal distribution.

Definition 1: Given $\{X_t\}$ a discrete time series and $q \in \mathbb{Z}_+^*$, elements of another time series $\{Y_t\}$ is defined by Equation 1.

$$Y_t = \frac{\sum_{r=0}^{q-1} X_{t+r}}{q} \quad (1)$$

For $t = 1, 2, \dots, n-q+1$, and n is the number of elements in $\{X_t\}$.

$\{Y_t\}$ is called the time series of *Moving Averages (MA)*.

The time series of MA is used to attenuate seasonal variations.

Definition 2: Given N observations X_1, X_2, \dots, X_N , on a discrete time series and $q \in \mathbb{Z}_+^*$, Equation 2 is the *Autocorrelation coefficient (AR coefficient)* of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_N , with lag q .

$$r_q = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N-q} (X_t - \bar{X})(X_{t+q} - \bar{X})}{\sum_{t=1}^N (X_t - \bar{X})^2} \quad (2)$$

Where \bar{X} is the mean of the time series.

In practice r_q is usually calculated since the autocovariance coefficients, $\{c_q\}$ with Equation 3 with the autocovariance coefficient with lag q .

$$c_q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^{N-q} (X_t - \bar{X})(X_{t+q} - \bar{X}) \quad (3)$$

Then, $r_q = \frac{c_q}{c_0}$.

To estimate the autocovariance it is recommendable to take $N > q+1$, $N \geq 50$ and $q \leq N/4$, see [17].

A *correlogram* is a graph that aids for interpreting the set of autocorrelation coefficients. It consists on a plot of lags q versus r_q .

A completely random time series, for a large N satisfies $r_q \approx 0$ for every q . This can be seen in the correlogram. Also, this kind of graph exhibits the presence of seasonal fluctuations in the original series when it has fluctuations as well.

The correlogram can contain the upper and lower bounds for autocorrelation with the significance level α , which is given by Equation 4:

$$B = \pm z_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} S(r_q) \quad (4)$$

Where r_q is the estimated autocorrelation of lag q , $z_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the quantile of the normal distribution and $S(\cdot)$ is calculated as follows:

$$S(r_1) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (5)$$

$$S(r_q) = \sqrt{\frac{1+2\sum_{i=1}^{q-1} r_i^2}{N}} \quad (6), \text{ for } q>1.$$

The trend is calculated by curve fitting of the time series observations, usually by means of a linear function and least square estimation.

MA and AR processes are used as models of time series. When they are combined or integrated they form the ARMA and ARIMA models, see [14, 17-18] for more details.

2.2 Neutrosophic Statistic

Neutrosophic Statistics is an extension of classical statistics where crisp numerical values are replaced by values in form of intervals, see [13][3]. This substitution can be applied to parameters, not only to random variables. The sample size can also be considered as indeterminate or inaccurate. In this theory the data can be ambiguous, vague, inaccurate, incomplete or indeterminate.

It is necessary to emphasize that there is a difference between the concepts of indeterminacy and randomness. Classical statistics deal with random variables, while in a neutrosophic framework they can also be indeterminate.

From this starting point, new concepts are defined from the classical ones, they are the following:

- *Neutrosophic Descriptive Statistics* “is comprised of all techniques to summarize and describe the neutrosophic numerical data characteristics.”
- *Neutrosophic Inferential Statistics* “consists of methods that permit the generalization from a neutrosophic sampling to a population from which it was selected the sample.”
- *Neutrosophic Data* “is the data that contains some indeterminacy.”
- *Neutrosophic Frequency Distribution* “is a table displaying the categories, frequencies, and relative frequencies with some indeterminacy.”
- *Neutrosophic Statistical Graphs* “are graphs that have indeterminate (unclear, vague, ambiguous, unknown) data or curves.”

Other essential definitions are the following:

Neutrosophic Survey Results “are survey results that contain some indeterminacy. A Neutrosophic Population is a population not well determined at the level of membership (i.e. not sure if some individuals belong or do not belong to the population).”

A *simple random neutrosophic sample of size n* from a classical or neutrosophic population is a sample of n individuals such that at least one of them has some indeterminacy.

Neutrosophic Random Numbers can also be generated using, instead of only crisp numbers, a pool of sets.

A *Neutrosophic Normal Distribution* of a continuous variable X is a classical normal distribution of x , but such that its mean μ or its standard deviation σ (or variance σ^2), or both, are imprecise.

Other neutrosophic distributions are: neutrosophic standard normal distribution, neutrosophic bivariate normal distribution, neutrosophic uniform distribution, neutrosophic sampling distribution, neutrosophic geometric distribution, neutrosophic hypergeometric distribution, neutrosophic Poisson distribution, neutrosophic chi-squared distribution, neutrosophic exponential distribution, neutrosophic frequency distribution, neutrosophic Pareto distribution and neutrosophic t-distribution.

The *Neutrosophic Least-Squares Lines* that approximates the neutrosophic bivariate data $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ has the same formula as in classical statistics, i.e.,

$\hat{y} = a + by$, where the slope $b = \frac{\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)/n}{\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2/n}$ and the y-intercept $a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x}$, where \bar{x} is the neutrosophic average of x , whereas \bar{y} is the neutrosophic average of y .

The *Neutrosophic Residuals* are computed in the same way as in classical statistics:

$y_1 - \hat{y}_1, y_2 - \hat{y}_2, \dots, y_n - \hat{y}_n$, where y_i are the real values of variable y , and \hat{y}_i are respectively their predicted values.

It is worthy to explain the definition and operations with neutrosophic numbers:

The *neutrosophic numbers* has the form $a+bI$, where a and b are real numbers, and $I =$ indeterminate.

Given $N_1 = a_1 + b_1I$ and $N_2 = a_2 + b_2I$ two neutrosophic numbers, some operations between them are defined as follows:

- $N_1 + N_2 = a_1 + a_2 + (b_1 + b_2)I$ (Addition);

- $N_1 - N_2 = a_1 - a_2 + (b_1 - b_2)I$ (Subtraction),
- $N_1 \times N_2 = a_1 a_2 + (a_1 b_2 + b_1 a_2 + b_1 b_2)I$ (Product),
- $\frac{N_1}{N_2} = \frac{a_1 + b_1 I}{a_2 + b_2 I} = \frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{a_2 b_1 - a_1 b_2}{a_2(a_2 + b_2)} I$ (Division).

Additionally, given $I_1 = [a_1, b_1]$ and $I_2 = [a_2, b_2]$ we have the following operations between them (see [19]):

- $I_1 + I_2 = [a_1 + a_2, b_1 + b_2]$ (Addition);
- $I_1 - I_2 = [a_1 - b_2, b_1 - a_2]$ (Subtraction),
- $I_1 \cdot I_2 = [\min\{a_1 \cdot b_1, a_1 \cdot b_2, a_2 \cdot b_1, a_2 \cdot b_2\}, \max\{a_1 \cdot b_1, a_1 \cdot b_2, a_2 \cdot b_1, a_2 \cdot b_2\}]$ (Product),
- $I_1 / I_2 = I_1 \cdot (1/I_2) = \{a/b : a \in I_1, b \in I_2\}$, always that $0 \notin I_2$ (Division).

3 Ecuadorian Tax Forecasting

Usually forecasting is referred to a unique value for every future time obtained from a unique model of prediction. However, the forecasted value is not necessarily accurate, in view that there not exists an ideal method of prediction. A very sophisticated method can yield to not sufficiently accurate results, while a simple one could be more accurate or vice versa.

In this paper we propose a method where the forecasted value is statistically obtained like an interval rather than a unique value. This predicted interval value is used to predict other value of the same kind and so on. Such a method is applied to forecast the Ecuadorian tax during 2019. It is based on the single-valued statistical forecasting methods which define an interval-valued one. We describe it below:

1. To graphically represent the time series and visually establish its properties of seasonal effect, cyclic changes and trend.
2. If $\{X_t\}$ for $t = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are the values of the time series. Apply the correlogram to statistically establish the seasonal effect.
3. Let $M_1(\{X_t\}), M_2(\{X_t\}), \dots, M_k(\{X_t\})$ be k forecasting methods conveniently selected according to some criteria of accuracy for this type of time series.
Obtain $X_{in+1} = M_i(\{X_t\})$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$; which are the forecasted values for every method at time t_{n+1} .
4. Form the intervals $I_{n+1} = [\min_i\{X_{in+1}\}, \max_i\{X_{in+1}\}]$. Now, we have new time series $\{X_t\}$ for $t = 1, 2, \dots, n, n+1$, where $X_{n+1} = I_{n+1}$.
5. Apply the Step 3 to the new $\{X_t\}$. In case that $\{X_t\}$ contains interval values, apply the prediction methods to both, the minimums and the maximums of the intervals and obtain a new value according to Step 3. In case that we have more than one interval instead of numeric values, we form the new interval that ranges from the minimum of every lower value to the maximum of every upper value of the input intervals.

This Step is applied until we predict the future values we needs in advance.

Let us remark that the precedent method, which we shall denote as $IM(S, n)$ for the time series S with n elements, allows predicting future values in form of intervals, i.e., we obtain $S_{n+1} = IM(S, n)$ the predicted $n+1$ value which is an interval-valued solution. Moreover, some elements of S can be intervals. Therefore, this is a kind of Neutrosophic Statistic method.

If we want to obtain a representative single value since $IM(S, n)$, we can calculate the following formula to interval $I_m = [a_1, a_2]$; see [20].

$$\lambda(I_m) = \frac{a_1 + a_2}{2} \quad (7)$$

The rationale of IM is the following, because every single-valued predicting method has its advantages and disadvantages over the other ones respect to accuracy, we cannot *a priori* establish which is the most appropriate method to solve the problem. But, if I_m is the interval that contains all these individual values obtained from the methods $M_1(\{X_t\}), M_2(\{X_t\}), \dots, M_k(\{X_t\})$; denoting by x_{in+1} the predicted single valued number corresponding to the i^{th} -method and $v(n+1)$ the actual unknown value to predict, then we can assume that $probability(v(n+1) \in I_m) \geq \max_i\{probability(v(n+1) = x_{in+1})\}$. Nevertheless, the cost for assuming this principle is that we increase the indeterminacy when we accept intervals rather than numbers as the predicted value.

Let us calculate the prediction of the Ecuadorian tax applying the precedent method. We support our calculus on the R language software Version 2.11.1, see [21][4]. The time series is the monthly observation of the taxes paid in Ecuador in thousand of USD collected as the sum of the income tax, consumption tax and value-added tax, which is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Depiction of the monthly time series of tax in Ecuador from 2014 to 2018.

For plotting we use the *plot* function of R. See that the series seems to have seasonal fluctuations, to determine this property we obtained the correlogram aided by the function *acf* of R, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Depiction of the correlogram of the tax time series.

The dotted lines in Figure 2 bound the interval of randomness. We can appreciate that the seasonal effect is more evident yearly, although there also exists a quarterly one.

The linear trend can be calculated from least squares fit obtaining the function $T(t) = 922349.3 + 1561.91 \cdot t$, which is graphically represented with the solid line in Figure 3. We used *lsfit* function of R. Let us appreciate that the trend is slightly increasing.

Figure 3: Tax time series with its linear trend.

For prediction we use the R functions *predict.ar*, *predict.Arima*, and *predict.StructTS*, which are based on

fitting methods using AR, ARIMA, and Maximum Likelihood respectively. We selected those methods because they are designed for time series prediction. The results are summarized in Table 1 and depicted in Figure 4.

Month	Lower prediction	Upper prediction	Middle prediction
January	887369.3	983527	935448.15
February	724684.8	970209.5	847447.15
March	964698.5	1311692	1138195.25
April	948233.3	1107685	1027959.15
May	813647	972354.5	893000.75
June	855445.6	972354.5	913900.05
July	965762.5	1140292	1053027.25
August	961802.7	1027133	994467.85
September	872498.3	1036670	954584.15
October	858309.4	992776.6	925543
November	940590.4	1086582	1013586.2
December	962525.2	1315634	1139079.6

Table 1: Predicted interval values for the year 2019 and the intermediate values x 1000 USD.

Figure 4: Depiction of the predicted interval values for the year 2019 and the intermediate values.

Let us note that in Figure 4 the upper line corresponds to the upper bound, the lower line corresponds to the lower bound and the intermediate line corresponds to the mean values, according to Equation 7.

Figure 5 contains the plotting of the degree of indeterminacy calculated according to Equation 8 given below. Let $I_m = [a_1, a_2]$ be an interval, the indeterminacy of I_m is calculated as follows:

$$\gamma(I_m) = a_2 - a_1 \tag{8}$$

Let us note that in Figure 5 the indeterminacy fluctuates over the time.

Figure 5: Depiction of the indeterminacy of predicted interval values.

Conclusion

This paper proposed a prediction method, where the future value is estimated in the form of an interval rather than in the form of a numeric value. Essentially, the method compiles the results of statistical prediction methods and converts them into a single value in form of an interval. This allows prediction of values with greater veracity, although with less precision. However, this is sufficiently useful to predict the behavior of taxes in Ecuador, in such a way that the monthly predictions of tax collection in Ecuador for the year 2019 are calculated.

References

- [1] Apolinsky, H. and Welch III, S. (2002). *J. K. Lasser' New Rules for Estate and Tax Planning*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [2] Guan, H., Guan, S. and Zhao, A. (2017). Forecasting Model Based on Neutrosophic Logical Relationship and Jaccard Similarity. *Symmetry*, 9(9), 191.
- [3] Guan, H., He, J., 2, A. Z., Dai, Z. and Guan, S. (2018). A Forecasting Model Based on Multi-Valued Neutrosophic Sets and Two-Factor, Third-Order Fuzzy Fluctuation Logical Relationships. *Symmetry*, 10(7), 245.
- [4] Abdel-Basset, M., Chang, V., Mohamed, M. and Smarandache, F. (2019). A Refined Approach for Forecasting Based on Neutrosophic Time Series. *Symmetry*, 11(4), 457.
- [5] Harrison, P. J. (1965). Short-Term Sales Forecasting. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series C (Applied Statistics)*, 14(2/3), 102-139.
- [6] Harrison, P. J. and Pearce, S. F. (1972). The Use of Trend Curves as an Aid to Market Forecasting. *Industrial Marketing Management* 2, 149-170.
- [7] Armstrong, J. S. (1984). Forecasting by Extrapolation: Conclusions from Twenty-five Years of Research. *Interfaces*, 14(6), 52-66.
- [8] Meade, N. (1984). The Use of Growth Curves in Forecasting Market Development-a Review and Appraisal. *Journal of Forecasting*, 3, 429-451. [1] M. L. VÁZQUEZ, N. B. HERNANDEZ, and F. SMARANDACHE, MÉTODOS MULTICRITERIOS PARA DETERMINACIÓN DE LA EFECTIVIDAD DE LA GESTIÓN PÚBLICA Y EL ANÁLISIS DE LA TRASPARENCIA: Infinite Study.
- [9] J. Estupiñan Ricardo, M. E. Llumiguano Poma, A. M. Argüello Pazmiño, A. D. Albán Navarro, L. Martín Estévez, and N. Batista Hernandez, "Neutrosophic model to determine the degree of comprehension of higher education students in Ecuador," *Neutrosophic Sets & Systems*, vol. 26, 2019.
- [10] N. B. Hernández, C. E. N. Luque, C. M. L. Segura, M. d. J. R. López, J. A. C. Hungria, and J. E. Ricardo, "LA TOMA DE DECISIONES EN LA INFORMÁTICA JURÍDICA BASADO EN EL USO DE LOS SISTEMAS EXPERTOS," *Investigación Operacional*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 131-139, 2019.
- [11] K. P. Teruel, M. Y. L. Vázquez, I. K. F. Cedeño, S. V. Jimenez, and I. D. M. Sanchidrian, "Modelo matemático y procedimiento para evaluación por complejidad de los requisitos software."
- [12] Armstrong, J. S. (1988). Research Needs in Forecasting. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 4(3), 449-465.
- [13] Allen, P. G. and Morzuch, B. J. (2006). Twenty-five years of progress, problems, and conflicting evidence in econometric forecasting. What about the next 25 years?. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 22(3), 475-492.
- [14] Armstrong, J. S. and Fildes, R. (2006). Making progress in forecasting *International Journal of Forecasting*, 22(3), 433-441.
- [15] Hang-Chan, N. and Palma, W. (2006). Estimation of Long-Memory Time Series Models: A Survey of different Likelihood-Based Methods. In *Econometric Analysis of Financial and Economic Time Series*. Amsterdam: Elsevier JAI.
- [16] Smarandache, F. (2014). *Introduction to Neutrosophic Statistics*. Craiova: Sitech & Education Publishing.
- [17] Chatfield, C. (1995). *The Analysis of Time Series: An Introduction*. Boca Raton: Chapman & Hall/CRC.
- [18] Hamilton, J. D. (1994). *Time Series Analysis*. Princeton Princeton University Press.
- [19] Kirchgässner, G. and Wolters, J. (2007). *Introduction to Modern Time Series Analysis*. Berlin: Springer-Verlag.
- [20] Pepió-Viñals, M. (2001). *Time Series (Series temporales)(In Spanish)*. Barcelona: Edicions UPC.
- [21] Box, G. E. P. and Pierce, D. A. (1970). Distribution of Residual Autocorrelations in Autoregressive-Integrated Moving Average Time Series Models. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 65(332), 1509-1526.
- [22] Moore, R. E. (1966). *Interval Analysis*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
- [23] R Development Core Team. (2010). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing: Reference Index: R Foundation for Statistical Computing.

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